

Prevalence Of Soil Transmitted Infection And Its Associated Factors In Pankshin Local Government Area Plateau State, Nigeria

^{1*}Muhammad Abubakar Jamilu; ²Binshak Nenrotnwa Bala; ²Abanise Mary Titilayo & ²Joseph Nagyal Mamani

¹Department of Biological Science,
Federal University Gashua, P. M. B. 1005, Yobe State, Nigeria
abusuraga1@gmail.com

²Department of Zoology,
Faculty of Natural Sciences
University of Jos, Jos, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

Nigeria stands as one of the countries bearing the highest burden of soil transmitted helminthes infections. This is attributed to several factors ranging from poor sanitation, open field defecation, inadequate toilet facilities, and poverty amongst others. However, The WHO has set a target of STH elimination by 2030 using periodic mass treatment of children in endemic areas. Hence, this study aimed was to determine the prevalence and intensity of STH infections and associated factors among residents of Pankshin Local Government Area, Plateau state. A community-based cross-sectional study was conducted among 525 (five hundred and twenty five) participants. A semi-structured questionnaire was used to collect data on socio-demographic and predisposing factors. The Kato-Katz concentration technique was utilized to detect and quantify the STH in collected stool samples. Both univariate and bivariate analyses were done while P-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant. The overall prevalence of Soil Transmitted Helminthes infection was 9.9% with *Ascaris lumbricoides* (45.5%), hookworms (21.8%), *Taenia* species (20%), and *Trichuri trichuria* (12.7%) identified. Age ($\chi^2=79.8$; $P<0.001$), gender ($\chi^2=79.8$; $P=<0.001$), occupation ($\chi^2=79.8$; $P<0.001$), availability of sanitary facilities ($\chi^2=79.8$; $P=<0.001$), and practice of open defecation ($\chi^2=79.8$; $P=<0.001$) were found to have statistically significant associations with the infection. However, the study recorded a low prevalence of STH in the study area, suggesting the success of such interventions in reducing transmission. However, open defecation and inadequate hygiene were particularly influential, emphasizing the persistent need for behavioral and infrastructure improvements. These findings reinforce the importance of targeted control measures and community-based strategies in sustaining low STH rates and preventing resurgence.

Keywords: Soil-transmitted helminthes, open defecation, infections

INTRODUCTION

Soil-transmitted helminthes (STH) infections are among the most prevalent infectious diseases globally, with about a quarter of the world's population affected (World Health Organization (WHO), 2025). The Global Burden of Disease (GBD) 2019 report highlights that up to 1.5 million disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) are lost annually due to STHs, and an additional 5.9 million people remain at risk of

acquiring these infections with the Sub-Saharan Africa, China, South America, and Asia (Agrawal et al., 2024). Soil-transmitted helminthes encompass a group of parasitic organisms, including *Ascaris lumbricoides*, *Trichuris trichiura*, and hookworms (*Ancylostoma duodenale* and *Necator americanus*). These infections disproportionately affect poor and marginalized communities, particularly in tropical and subtropical areas where access to clean water, sanitation, and hygiene facilities is limited (Moncayo, 2018).

Soil-transmitted helminthes infections cause both nutritional and physical impairments in children, and increase the risk of maternal and infant mortality as well as low birth weight in women (WHO, 2025). These infections are transmitted through eggs found in human feces, which contaminate the soil in areas with inadequate sanitation (WHO, 2025). The eggs can attach to vegetables and are ingested when the vegetables are not properly washed, peeled, or cooked, or through contaminated water sources (WHO, 2025). This emphasizes proper water and food hygiene.

Prevention methods include health education aimed at curtailing infection and re-infection. Additionally, improving sanitation is crucial to reduce soil contamination with infective eggs (WHO, 2025). Safe and effective medicines are also available for controlling infection. This includes periodic deworming with albendazole (400 mg) and mebendazole (500 mg), which help eliminate infecting worms (WHO, 2025).

In Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), helminthes infections account for approximately 85% of neglected tropical diseases, with hookworm infection affecting nearly half of the region's poorest communities (Zeynudin et al., 2022). Despite efforts, STH infections continue to pose a significant socio-economic challenge and remain a major public health issue in many SSA countries (Lwanga et al., 2012). Nigeria, in particular, remains the most endemic country with records of all four common STH species (Hotez & Kamath, 2009; Hotez et al., 2012). The country alone has 774 implementation units (IUs) where preventive chemotherapy (PC) programs are carried out.

In Nigeria, several associated factors contribute to the prevalence of STH infections. These include poor sanitation, limited access to clean water, lack of proper hygiene practices, and inadequate healthcare infrastructure (WHO, 2025). Environmental factors, such as the use of untreated water for drinking and irrigation, as well as agricultural practices where contaminated soil is not adequately managed, also play a role. Additionally, socio-economic factors such as poverty, low levels of education, and limited awareness of hygiene and sanitation practices further exacerbate the risk of STH transmission in the area (Adewale et al., 2023; Deme et al., 2019). These factors continue to contribute to the high prevalence of these infections and making elimination unachievable.

The WHO has set a target to eliminate STH by 2030 (WHO, 2023). To achieve this, it is important to gather evidence on the burden of STH, particularly in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), where the disease remains highly prevalent. This knowledge is critical for achieving the goals outlined in the 2020–2030 NTD road map for the elimination of STH (World Health Organization, 2020; Bisoffi et al., 2020; World Health Organization, 2012).

Several individual studies have examined the prevalence of STH, which could guide the government and relevant organizations in prioritizing and developing appropriate strategies for controlling and preventing STH infections. Thus, providing updated prevalence and intensity data in areas previously classified as non-endemic is crucial for informed decision-making and effective implementation, especially when transmission patterns are changing. Hence, this study aims to assess the prevalence of STH infections in Pankshin LGA and identify the associated factors contributing to its spread.

METHODOLOGY

Study Design

A community-based cross-sectional study was conducted in Pankshin is a Local Government Area in Central Plateau State Nigeria with the headquarter in Pankshin town. It has an area of 1.524Km², located at 9° 20' 0" North and 9° 27' 0" East above sea level. Pankshin is well known for its relatively cool temperature and the annual temperature is 22°C and the rainfall averages is 1150millimeters (45in). The range of temperatures could be hottest between April to early June while heavy rainfalls are between late June to mid-August. The coldest temperature can be felt in mid-November to late February, January being

the coldest month (Moodle, 2019). The sites include Gille, from Wokkos District and Wulmi from Pankshin District. Gille is located on a hill with swampy areas. The inhabitants are predominantly farmers as they mostly grow vegetables. The soil texture in this study is loamy and very fertile. Wulmi village is located near the Pankshin Dam. The soil type is sandy. The inhabitants are predominantly farmers while some are fishermen.

Sample size and sampling procedure

The sample size was determined using a single population proportion formula. By using a marginal error of 5%, a 95% confidence interval, and 10% non-response rates, the total sample size was calculated to be 525 inhabitants of the community. Using the stratified random sampling method, the sample size for each (stratum) was determined by proportionate allocation to the total number of households in the communities. The head of the household in each of the selected households in the communities was selected and asked for consent to be included in the study.

Qualitative data collection and processing

Data on socio-demographic characteristics and hygiene practices, for STH infections, were collected using a pretested semi-structured questionnaire and a checklist prepared for the purpose of this study. The questionnaire was first prepared in English and then translated into the local language. Trained research assistant collected the qualitative data from each of the household heads after obtaining written informed consent.

Stool collection and examination

About 5 grams of stool were collected from each participant by a trained technologist using labeled, sterile containers. Samples were checked for proper labeling and volume, then transported to the Zoology laboratory in University of Jos within two hours. A single Kato-Katz smear was prepared and examined microscopically to identify soil-transmitted helminth eggs and assess infection intensity, following WHO guidelines (WHO, 2019). Slides were read 20–30 minutes after preparation to improve hookworm detection (Bosch *et al.*, 2021; Zeynudin *et al.*, 2022).

Statistical analysis

Data were entered into a Microsoft Excel database and analyzed using GraphPad Prism version 8.0.1.244. Descriptive statistics were computed, and Pearson's chi-square (χ^2) test was used to evaluate the association between variables and prevalence rates. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical Clearance

An introductory letter was issued by the Head of the Zoology Department, University of Jos, to the Director of Health, Pankshin Local Government. Permission was granted through the Monitoring and Evaluation Unit of the Health Department. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, who voluntarily completed the questionnaires and submitted their urine and stool samples for analysis.

RESULTS

Table 1: Sociodemographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Characteristics	Frequency (N=525)	Percentage (%)
Age groups		
<10	140	26.7
11-20	99	18.9
21-30	75	14.3
31-40	65	12.4
41-50	69	13.1
51-60	43	8.1
61-70	26	5.0
>70	8	1.5
Gender		
Female	247	47.0
Male	278	53.0
Occupation		
Student	133	25.3
Farmer	139	26.5
Fisherman	98	18.7
Civil servant	90	17.1
others	65	12.4
Availability of sanitary utilities		
Yes	399	76.0
No	126	24.0
Practice open defecation		
Yes	72	13.7
No	453	86.3

Table 1 presents the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents. The respondents show diverse age distribution, with the largest proportion (26.7%) in the <10 age group. Similarly, males (53.0%) slightly outnumbered females (47.0%). The majority of respondents reported having access to sanitary utilities (76.0%), while a small proportion (13.7%) practiced open defecation. Most respondents fell into the low-income category (59.4%), followed by medium-income (36.4%) and high-income (4.2%). Occupation-wise, farmers (26.5%) and students (25.3%) formed the largest groups.

Prevalence of STH in the study Area

Figure 1: Prevalence of Soil Transmitted Helminthiasis among the study population

A low prevalence rate (9.9%) infection was recorded among the study population.

Figure 2: Prevalence of Helminth Eggs in the Study Area

The most frequently identified helminths in the study population were *Ascaris lumbricoides* (45.5%), hookworms (21.8%), *Taenia species* (20%), and *Trichuri trichuria* (12.7%).

Table 2: Factors associated with the Prevalence of Soil Transmitted Helminthiasis

Characteristics	Frequency (N)%		χ^2	P-value
	Infected 52(9.9)	Not infected 473(90.1)		
Age groups				
<10	4(2.9)	136(97.1)	79.8	<0.01*
11-20	25(25.3)	74(74.7)		
21-30	1(1.4)	74(98.6)		
31-40	1(1.5)	64(98.5)		
41-50	20(29.0)	49(71.0)		
51-60	1(2.3)	42(97.7)		
61-70	0(0)	26(100)		
>70	0(0)	8(100)		
Gender				
Female	38(15.4)	209(74.6)	3.96	<0.01*
Male	14(5.0)	264(95.0)		
Occupation				
Student	17(12.8)	116(87.2)	15.30	0.004*
Farmer	21(15.1)	118(74.9)		
Fisherman	10(10.2)	88(89.8)		
Civil servant	1(1.1)	89(98.9)		
Others	3(4.6)	62(95.4)		
Availability sanitary facilities				
Yes	10(2.5)	389(97.5)	102.0	<0.01*
No	42(33.3)	84(66.7)		
Practice open defecation				
Yes	29(40.3)	43(59.7)	86.26	<0.01*
No	23(5.1)	430(94.9)		
Income of Level				
Low	33(10.6)	279(89.4)	0.39	0.82
Medium	17(8.9)	174(91.1)		
High	2(10.0)	20(90.0)		

* P value <0.05 which is statistically significant

Age, gender, occupation, availability of sanitary facilities, and practice of open defecation were factors significantly associated with the prevalence of Soil Transmitted Helminthiasis.

DISCUSSION

The study determined the prevalence of soil-transmitted helminths (STH), identified the species present, and examined associated factors in Pankshin LGA of Plateau State. A low STH prevalence (9.9%) was recorded, which aligns with similarly low rates reported in Ethiopia (Zeynudin et al., 2022) and India (Christu Rajan et al., 2020). In contrast, higher prevalences have been reported in Gwagwalada (Deme et al., 2019), Imo State (Odinaka et al., 2015), Osun State (Salawu & Ughele, 2019), and Ogun State (Idowu et al., 2022). This disparity may be attributed to differences in study populations, as those studies focused exclusively on school-aged children.

The lower prevalence observed in the present study may reflect the impact of Mass Drug Administration (MDA) programs supported by the WHO, which have significantly reduced STH rates. While higher rates in other regions may result from less extensive MDA coverage, this finding underscores the importance of effective interventions such as deworming campaigns and improved sanitation in controlling STH transmission. Continued monitoring and expansion of these programs are essential to prevent a resurgence of infections.

The most frequently identified helminths in the study population were *Ascaris lumbricoides*, hookworms, *Taenia* species (20%), and *Trichuris trichiura* (12.7%). These findings reflect the distribution pattern of infections among participants and are consistent with results from studies conducted in Ogun State (Idowu et al., 2022) and Ethiopia (Zeynudin et al., 2022).

Similar to other reports of Mordi and Ngwodo, (2007), *A. lumbricoides* was the most prevalent species, followed in order by hookworms and *T. trichiura*. Nonetheless, some investigations have noted a higher dominance of hookworm infections (Taiwo et al., 2017; Kamalu et al., 2013). These discrepancies may be influenced by socio-economic factors, particularly in rural settings. In the present study, participants exhibited limited access to sanitation facilities and practiced open defecation. These conditions, along with inadequate hygiene practices, likely contributed to the higher infection rates of *A. lumbricoides* and hookworms.

Age and gender were significant determinants of STH prevalence, with children and younger individuals more vulnerable to helminth infections due to increased exposure to contaminated environments and suboptimal hygiene practices. This is consistent with previous findings from studies by Christu Rajan et al. (2020) and Zeynudin et al. (2020). Gender differences also influenced STH risk, aligning with the suggestion by Christu Rajan et al. (2020) that gender-based roles may affect exposure levels. The current study supports this by highlighting that daily activities such as outdoor labor or caregiving duties could increase susceptibility to infection.

Occupation was also associated with higher STH prevalence, particularly among individuals involved in agriculture or manual labor, a finding supported by Adewale et al. (2023) in their study from India. Additionally, access to sanitation facilities emerged as a key determinant across settings. This finding mirrors prior research (Christu Rajan et al., 2020; Mordi et al., 2007; WHO, 2025; Taiwo et al., 2017), which emphasized the link between inadequate sanitation and sustained helminth transmission.

Open defecation practices were strongly correlated with STH prevalence, reinforcing earlier evidence from Mordi et al. (2007), WHO (2025), and Taiwo et al. (2017), which connected such practices to increased environmental contamination. The present study underscores the need to eliminate open defecation as a critical step in reducing the burden of helminth infections.

CONCLUSION

This study recorded a low prevalence (9.9%) of STH in Pankshin LGA of Plateau State, suggesting the success of such interventions in reducing STH transmission. The dominant species identified were *Ascaris lumbricoides*, hookworms, *Taenia* spp., and *Trichuris trichiura*, reflecting common patterns of infection in resource-limited settings with poor sanitation. The study also found significant associations between STH prevalence and factors such as gender, occupation, hygiene practices, and access to sanitation facilities. Open defecation and inadequate hygiene were particularly influential, emphasizing the persistent need for behavioral and infrastructure improvements.

However, the study recommends that

- i. Government, ministry of health and community leaders should intensify community awareness programs on proper hygiene and the risks of open defecation to reduce STH transmission.
- ii. Governments and stakeholders should prioritize the provision of affordable, accessible, and sustainable sanitation infrastructure.
- iii. Regular deworming campaigns, particularly in high-risk groups such as children and manual laborers, should be continued and expanded to reach underserved populations.
- iv. Government should encourage community ownership of sanitation improvements by adopting participatory approaches like community led total sanitation (CLTS), aimed at eliminating open defecation and promoting behavioral change.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST & FUNDING

None

REFERENCES

- Adewale, B., Mogaji, H., Balogun, J., Balogun, E., Olamiju, F., & Herbert, D. (2023). Monitoring the status of soil-transmitted helminthiasis in non-endemic implementation units: A case study of Borgu in Northcentral Nigeria. *Pathogens*, 12(3), 491. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens12030491>
- Agrawal, R., Pattnaik, S., Kshatri, J. S., Kanungo, S., Mandal, N., Palo, S. K., & Pati, S. (2024). Prevalence and correlates of soil-transmitted helminths in schoolchildren aged 5 to 18 years in low- and middle-income countries: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 12, 1283054. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2024.1283054>
- Bisoffi, Z., et al. (2020). The global progress of soil-transmitted helminthiasis control in 2020 and World Health Organization targets for 2023. *PLoS Neglected Tropical Diseases*, 14(11), e0008505. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pntd.0008505>
- Bosch, F., Palmeirim, M. S., Ali, S. M., Ame, S. M., Hattendorf, J., & Keiser, J. (2021). Diagnosis of soil-transmitted helminths using the Kato-Katz technique: What is the influence of stirring, storage time and storage temperature on stool sample egg counts? *PLOS Neglected Tropical Diseases*, 15(1), e0009032. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pntd.0009032>
- Christu Rajan, V. X., Sivamani, M., & Appalaraju, B. (2020). Prevalence and the factors influencing soil-transmitted helminths among school age children (5–14 years age) in a rural area of Coimbatore district. *Tropical Parasitology*, 10(2), 74–78. https://doi.org/10.4103/tp.TP_33_19
- Expanded Special Project for Elimination of Neglected Tropical Diseases (ESPEN). (2022). *Nigeria*. <https://espen.afro.who.int/countries/nigeria>
- Federal Ministry of Health (FMOH). (2020). *Neglected tropical diseases master plan 2015–2020*. World Health Organization. https://espen.afro.who.int/system/files/content/resources/NIGERIA_NTD_Master_Plan_2015_2020.pdf
- Hotez, P. J., & Kamath, A. (2009). Neglected tropical diseases in Sub-Saharan Africa: Review of their prevalence, distribution, and disease burden. *PLoS Neglected Tropical Diseases*, 3(8), e412. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pntd.0000412>
- Hotez, P. J., Asojo, O., & Adesina, A. M. (2012). Nigeria: “Ground zero” for the high prevalence neglected tropical diseases. *PLoS Neglected Tropical Diseases*, 6(3), e1600. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pntd.0001600>
- Idowu, O. A., Babalola, A. S., & Olapegba, T. (2022). Prevalence of soil-transmitted helminth infection among children under 2 years from urban and rural settings in Ogun state, Nigeria: Implication for control strategy. *Egyptian Pediatric Association Gazette*, 70, 5. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43054-021-00096-6>
- Kamalu, N. A., Uwakwe, F. E., & Opara, J. A. (2013). Prevalence of intestinal parasite among high school students in Nigeria. *Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*, 2(7), 9–16.
- Lwanga, F., Kirunda, B. E., & Orach, C. G. (2012). Intestinal helminth infections and nutritional status of children attending primary schools in Wakiso district, Central Uganda. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 9(8), 2910–2921. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph9082910>
- Moncayo, A. L., Lovato, R., & Cooper, P. J. (2018). Soil-transmitted helminth infections and nutritional status in Ecuador: Findings from a national survey and implications for control strategies. *BMJ Open*, 8, e021319. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2017-021319>
- Mordi, R. M., & Ngwodo, P. O. A. (2007). A study of blood and gastrointestinal parasites in Edo state. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 6(19), 2201–2207.
- Taiwo, O. T., Sam-Wobo, S. O., Idowu, O. A., Talabi, A. O., & Taiwo, M. (2017). Comparative assessment of intestinal helminths prevalence in water, sanitation and hygiene (WASH) intervention and non-intervention communities in Abeokuta, Nigeria. *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Biomedicine*, 7(6), 524–532. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apjtb.2017.05.007>

- World Health Organization. (2012). *Eliminating soil-transmitted helminthiases as a public health problem in children: Progress report 2001–2010 and strategic plan 2011–2020*. World Health Organization. https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/44804/9789241503129_eng.pdf
- World Health Organization. (2019). *Bench aids for the diagnosis of intestinal parasites*. <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/330611>
- World Health Organization. (2020). *Ending the neglect to attain the sustainable development goals: A road map for neglected tropical diseases 2021–2030*. World Health Organization. <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240062884>
- World Health Organization. (2023). *2030 targets for soil-transmitted helminthiases control programmes*. <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/330611>
- World Health Organization. (2025). *Soil-transmitted helminth (STH) infections*. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/soil-transmitted-helminth-infections>
- Zeynudin, A., Degefa, T., Tesfaye, M., Suleman, S., Yesuf, E. A., et al. (2022). Prevalence and intensity of soil-transmitted helminth infections and associated risk factors among household heads living in the peri-urban areas of Jimma town, Oromia, Ethiopia: A community-based cross-sectional study. *PLOS ONE*, 17(9), e0274702. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0274702>